

Table S1. Cyanobacterial and chytrid biovolume in uninfected and infected cyanobacterial cultures ($n = 5$).

Condition	Treatment	Cyanobacterial biovolume (mm ³ L ⁻¹)	Chytrid biovolume (mm ³ L ⁻¹)	Total biovolume (mm ³ L ⁻¹)	% Cyanob.	% Chytrid
Uninfected	Control	68.53	0.00	68.53	100.0	0.0
Uninfected	MET	80.94	0.00	80.94	100.0	0.0
Uninfected	CB	90.29	0.00	90.29	100.0	0.0
Infected	Control	117.14	0.82	117.96	99.3	0.7
Infected	MET	164.70	1.27	165.97	99.2	0.8
Infected	CB	120.77	0.78	121.56	99.4	0.6

Table S2. Linear effect models predicting infection prevalence, infection intensity and biomarker responses.

Effect	Infection prevalence (df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.65)		Infection intensity (df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.39)		Proteins uninfected (df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.40)		Proteins infected (df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.42)	
	Estimate (± s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value	Estimate (± s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value	Estimate (± s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value	Estimate (± s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value
Intercept	9.7 ± 1.19	8.17	7.3 ± 1.54	4.74	2.80 ± 0.86	32.61	9.2 ± 1.53	6.03
MET	1.6 ± 1.68	0.95	4.6 ± 2.18	2.11	-0.26 ± 0.12	-2.12	-5.4 ± 2.16	-2.50
CB	-6.7 ± 1.68	-3.99	-2.5 ± 2.18	-1.15	-0.4 ± 0.12	-3.30	1.8 ± 2.16	0.83

Table S2. (continued)

Effect	Lipids uninfected (df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.47)		Lipid infected (df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.21)		TBARS uninfected (df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.41)		TBARS infected (df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.42)	
	Estimate (± s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value	Estimate (± s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value	Estimate (± s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value	Estimate (± s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value
Intercept	11.8 ± 1.46	8.09	11.0 ± 1.78	6.18	12.2 ± 1.54	7.91	11.4 ± 1.53	7.45
MET	-3.6 ± 2.06	-1.75	-6.0 ± 2.52	-2.38	-5.6 ± 2.18	-2.57	-7.4 ± 2.16	-3.42
CB	-7.8 ± 2.06	-3.79	-3.0 ± 2.52	-1.19	-7.0 ± 2.18	-3.21	-2.8 ± 2.16	-1.29

Table S2. (continued)

Effect	SOD uninfected (df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.48)		SOD infected (df = 12; adj. R^2 = -0.06)		GST uninfected (df = 12; adj. R^2 = -0.06)		GST infected (df = 12; adj. R^2 = -0.12)	
	Estimate (± s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value	Estimate (± s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value	Estimate (± s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value	Estimate (± s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value
Intercept	4.8 ± 1.44	3.33	8.6 ± 2.06	4.17	6.2 ± 2.06	3.01	8.6 ± 2.12	4.06
MET	2.0 ± 2.04	0.98	-2.4 ± 2.91	-0.82	3.0 ± 2.91	1.03	6.08 ± 3.00	0
CB	7.6 ± 2.04	3.73	0.60 ± 2.91	0.21	2.4 ± 2.91	0.82	-1.8 ± 3.00	-0.60

Table S3. Percentage of microcystins in infected and uninfected cultures. Values represent the mean \pm sd, ($n = 5$).

Status	Treatment	DMC-RR (%)	DMC-LR (%)	MC X (%)
Uninfected	Control	90.7 \pm 0.73	8.6 \pm 0.73	0.7 \pm 0.02
Uninfected	MET	93.1 \pm 1.43	6.4 \pm 1.36	0.5 \pm 0.07
Uninfected	CB	91.2 \pm 0.60	8.2 \pm 0.61	0.7 \pm 0.02
Infected	Control	94.6 \pm 0.30	4.9 \pm 0.32	0.5 \pm 0.04
Infected	MET	91.2 \pm 1.06	8.3 \pm 1.08	0.6 \pm 0.02
Infected	CB	95.0 \pm 0.25	4.6 \pm 0.24	0.4 \pm 0.04

Table S4. Linear effect models predicting MC concentrations.

Effect	Uninfected		Infected	
	Estimate (\pm s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value	Estimate (\pm s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value
DMC-RR total	df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.34		df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.55	
Intercept	11 \pm 1.63	6.75	9.2 \pm 1.35	6.82
MET	-2.2 \pm 2.31	-0.95	-5.8 \pm 1.91	-3.04
CB	-6.8 \pm 2.31	-2.95	2.20 \pm 1.91	0.27
DMC-RR intracellular	df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.34		df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.55	
Intercept	11.0 \pm 1.63	6.75	9.2 \pm 1.35	6.82
MET	-2.2 \pm 2.31	-0.95	-5.8 \pm 1.91	-3.04
CB	-6.8 \pm 2.31	-2.95	2.2 \pm 1.91	1.15
DMC-RR extracellular	df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.24		df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.44	
Intercept	11.2 \pm 1.75	6.4	11.8 \pm 1.50	7.85
MET	-3.4 \pm 2.47	-1.37	-3.8 \pm 2.13	-1.79
CB	-6.2 \pm 2.47	-2.51	-7.6 \pm 2.13	-3.58
DMC-LR total	df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.42		df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.50	
Intercept	11.0 \pm 1.53	7.21	0.34 \pm 0.03	12.19
MET	-1.8 \pm 2.16	-0.83	-0.16 \pm 0.04	-4.02
CB	-7.2 \pm 2.16	-3.34	-0.08 \pm 0.04	-2.01
DMC-LR intracellular	df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.42		df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.48	
Intercept	11.0 \pm 1.53	7.21	0.34 \pm 0.03	11.94
MET	-1.8 \pm 2.16	-0.83	-0.16 \pm 0.04	-3.89
CB	-7.2 \pm 2.16	-3.34	-0.08 \pm 0.04	-1.91
DMC-LR extracellular	df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.065		df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.41	
Intercept	10.6 \pm 1.93	5.48	11.0 \pm 1.08	10.22
MET	-3.2 \pm 2.74	-1.17	-4.5 \pm 1.52	-2.96
CB	-4.6 \pm 2.74	-1.68	-4.5 \pm 1.52	-2.96
MC X total	df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.47		df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.22	
Intercept	11.0 \pm 1.46	7.52	10.4 \pm 5.87	5.87

MET	-1.6 ± 2.07	-0.77	-5.8 ± 2.51	-2.31
CB	-7.4 ± 2.07	-3.58	-1.4 ± 2.51	-0.56
MC X intracelullar	df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.47		df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.22	
Intercept	11.0 ± 1.46	7.52	10.4 ± 1.77	5.87
MET	-1.6 ± 2.07	-0.77	-5.8 ± 2.51	-2.31
CB	-7.4 ± 2.07	-3.58	-1.4 ± 2.51	-0.56
MC X extracelullar	df = 12; adj. R^2 = -0.12		all data points were below the detection limit	
Intercept	7.6 ± 1.65	4.62		
MET	1.4 ± 2.33	0.60		
CB	-2.0 ± 2.33	-0.09		

Table S5. Linear effect models with interaction predicting metolachlor, nicotine and cotinine concentrations, as well as IBRv2. Estimates significant at the $p < 0.05$ level are bold.

Effect	Estimate (\pm s.e.)	<i>t</i> -value	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i> -value
Metolachlor				
	df = 16; adj. R^2 = 0.32			
Intercept	9.5 \pm 2.18	4.35		
Day \times Condition			0.13	0.72
Day			3.03	0.1
Condition			9.4	0.007
Nicotine				
	df = 16; adj. R^2 = 0.42			
Intercept	13.6 \pm 2.02	6.75		
Day \times Condition			0.01	0.92
Day			16.74	0.0008
Condition			1.05	0.32
Cotinine				
	df = 12; adj. R^2 = 0.81			
Intercept	5.1 \pm 1.15	4.42		
Day \times Condition			3.32	0.09
Day			64.86	< 0.0001
Condition			5.96	0.026
IBRv2				
	df = 24; adj. R^2 = 0.45			
Intercept	2.7 \pm 0.31	8.67		
Treatment \times			7.32	0.003
Condition				

†: F test performed on nested models. In models where the interaction was significant, we did not test the significance of individual fixed effects.

Table S6. Linear effect models predicting cyanobacteria biovolume.

Effect	Estimate (\pm s.e.)	Variance (\pm s.d.)	Degrees of freedom	<i>t</i> -value
Cyanobacteria biovolume of uninfected cultures (cond. $R^2 = 0.309$; marg. $R^2 = 0.073$)^a				
Intercept	8.03 \pm 0.49		12	16.43
MET	0.81 \pm 0.69		12	1.164
CB	1.29 \pm 0.69		12	1.867
Sample		0.92 \pm 0.96		
Residual		2.71 \pm 1.65		
Cyanobacteria biovolume of infected cultures (cond. $R^2 = 0.330$; marg. $R^2 = 0.159$)^a				
Intercept	10.60 \pm 0.51		12	20.65
MET	2.08 \pm 0.73		12	2.86
CB	0.21 \pm 0.73		12	0.28
Sample		0.95 \pm 0.97		
Residual		3.70 \pm 1.93		

^aCond. R^2 : conditional R^2 describes the proportion of total variance explained by the fixed effects and the random effects together; marg. R^2 : marginal R^2 describes the proportion of total variance explained exclusively by the fixed effects. Root square transform data was used for the models.

Figure S1. Total, intracellular and extracellular DMC-LR concentrations in cyanobacteria exposed to chemical pollutants with and without chytrid parasites. DMC-LR concentrations were adjusted to the cyanobacterial biovolume of each replicate per treatment and condition. Boxes indicate the upper and lower quartiles, the dark middle line indicates the median, whiskers indicate 1.5 times the interquartile range and black points represent outliers ($n = 5$). MET: metolachlor; CB: cigarette butt leachate; DMC-LR tot: MC-LR total; DMC-LR int: MC-LR intracellular and DMC-LR ext: MC-LR extracellular.

Figure S2. Total, intracellular and extracellular MC X concentrations in cyanobacteria exposed to chemical pollutants with and without chytrid parasites. MC X concentrations were adjusted to the cyanobacterial biovolume of each replicate per treatment and condition. Boxes indicate upper and lower quartiles, the dark middle line indicates the median, whiskers indicate 1.5 times the interquartile range and black points represent outliers ($n = 5$). MET: metolachlor; CB: cigarette butt leachate; MC X tot: MC X total; MC X int: MC X intracellular; MC X ext: MC X extracellular.

Figure S3. Glutathione *S*-transferase activity in cyanobacteria exposed to chemical pollutants with and without chytrid parasites. GST activity was adjusted to the protein content of each replicate per treatment and condition. Boxes indicate the upper and lower quartiles, the dark middle line indicates the median, whiskers indicate 1.5 times the interquartile range and black points represent outliers ($n = 5$). MET: metolachlor; CB: cigarette butt leachate; GST: glutathione *S*-transferase.

Figure S4. Metolachlor, nicotine and cotinine concentrations in cyanobacteria exposed to chemical pollutants with and without chytrid parasites. Boxes indicate upper and lower quartiles, the dark middle line indicates the median, whiskers indicate 1.5 times the interquartile range and black points represent outliers ($n = 5$).

Figure S5. Cyanobacterial biovolume and parasite fitness proxies. A) Cyanobacterial biovolume, B) infection prevalence (percentage of infected cyanobacterial filaments), and C) infection intensity (mean infections number per infected filament). Boxes indicate the upper and lower quartiles, the dark middle line indicates the median, whiskers indicate 1.5 times the interquartile range and black points represent outliers ($n = 5$). MET: metolachlor; CB: cigarette butt leachate.